

Study of Hormone Receptor Status in Breast Cancer and its Relation to Age and Other Prognostic Factors

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Abstract:

Background: Increasing evidence shows the importance of young age, estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR) status, and HER-2 expression in patients with breast cancers.

Methods: We organized an analytic cross-sectional study of 105 women diagnosed with breast cancer who have been operated at Department of Surgery, GMCH, Bettiah, W. Champaran, Bihar from March 2023 to January 2024. We evaluated age, size, hormone receptor status, HER-2 and P53 expression as possible indicator of lymph node involvement.

Results: There is a direct correlation between positive progesterone receptor status and being younger than 40 ($P < 0.05$). Also, compared with older women, young women had tumors that were more likely to be large in size and have higher stages ($P < 0.05$). Furthermore patients with negative progesterone receptor status were more likely to have HER-2 overexpression ($P < 0.05$). The differences in propensity to lymph node metastasis between hormone receptor statuses were not statically significant.

Conclusion: Although negative progesterone receptor tumors were more likely to have HER-2 overexpression, it is possible that higher stage and larger size breast cancer in younger women is related to positive progesterone receptor status.

Keywords: Breast Cancer, Estrogen Receptor, Progesterone Receptor, Lymph Node Metastasis, Age.

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Introduction

A growing number of cases every year for almost all types of cancers is the cause of concern for the present medical system. The rising death toll irrespective of age, sex and geographical locations and lack of a cure, made the situation alarming and warrant immediate action from the global scientific and medical communities. For women, scientific breast cancer is observed in almost all age groups irrespective of the geographical location and race a person belong to. The WHO based Globocan cancer monitoring and survey Analysis suggested that in 2018 alone, 2,088,849 (11.6%) new cases have been reported in all age groups for men and women together. [1]

In the same year, the number of the death toll due to breast cancer was reported as 6,26,679, i.e., 6.6% of the total death (9,555,027) caused by cancer. Among Indian women, breast cancer turned out to be the most lethal form of cancer with an average age-adjusted rate of 25.8/100,000 women

and calculated mortality of 12.7/100,000 women. [2] Detail inspection of the data suggested that the higher age-adjusted cases were observed in Delhi (41), Chennai (37.9) and Bangalore (34.4) followed by Thiruvananthapuram District (33.7). [2]

Estimations suggested that the number of cases is higher in the urban and metropolitan regions of India whereas reports are less in the rural areas. Surprisingly, the mortality-to-incidence ratio has shown an opposite outcome with 66 in rural and 8 in the urban region. Age, genetic makeup and genes, economic condition, lifestyle, food habits, cultural beliefs, awareness, frequency of medical checkup are vital in relation to the disease onset and progression. [3-7] The prognostic effect of somatic mutation in ER-positive breast cancers and emphasized on the TP53, NF1, PIK3CA, and PIK3R1 genes as the prognostic driver irrespective of the clinical variables accounted for a particular case. [8] Thus, understanding the

relationship of breast cancer with hormone receptor status and relevant prognostic factors is of immense importance. With this objective, we have attempted to focus on the correlation of these factors in women less than 45 years of age with respect to hormone receptor status (ER/PR). In this study, correlation of hormone receptor status (ER/PR) with lymph node status and histopathological grading and staging of breast cancer was investigated for the patients under 45 years of age.

Material and Methods

The study population consisted of 105 patients with unilateral breast cancer treated by modified radical mastectomy with axillary dissection at Surgery Department of Govt. Medical College & Hospital, Bettiah, West Champaran, Bihar from March 2023 to January 2024. All types of histologically confirmed invasive carcinoma were included.

The information was extracted retrospectively and included patient age, tumor size, stage, histologic type, estrogen and progesterone receptor status, P53, and HER-2 expression. Each of these factors was separately evaluated for correlation with lymph node involvement and degree of positivity defined as number of nodes with metastases.

All analyses were done in a single laboratory using the same method, eliminating the problem of inter laboratory differences. Patients were divided into two age groups: <40 years and \geq 40 years.

Patient and tumor characteristics of age, tumor size in cm (\leq 2 or T1, 2 to 5 or T2, \geq 5 or T3, and T4), number of nodes involved (none or N0, one to three or N1, four to nine or N2, more than ten or N3, and unknown), stage (I, II, III, IV, and unstaged), estrogen receptor (ER), progesterone receptor (PR) (positive and negative), P53 expression, HER-2 expression (positive and negative), and laterality

were recorded. Tumor size was measured from the largest diameter in the gross specimen.

Hormone receptors were considered negative when concentration was below 10%. P53 was considered positive when nuclear staining was positive in more than 10% of tumoral cells. HER-2/neu overexpression was considered positive when complete and intense membrane staining was observed in more than 10% of tumoral cells.

The chi-square test was used for statistical analysis for categorical variables. If the expected number in any cell of the 2×2 contingency table was less than five, Fischer's exact test was used. As the analysis involves multiple subgroups, significance was set at the 5% level ($P < 0.05$). The data was analyzed using SPSS v.13.0 and EPI Info 6.0.

Results

The distribution of patients by age classifications was as follows: 18 patients (17.1%) were younger than 40 years old, and 87 patients (82.8%) were 40 years and older.

Mean age at diagnosis in the younger women was 34 years (range 27 to 39 years) compared with a mean age of 53 years in the older women (range 40 to 80 years).

Stage distribution of the tumors was as follows: Stage I: 13 patients (12.3%), stage II: 40 patients (38.1%), stage III: 47 patients (44.7%), stage IV: 3 patients (2.8%) and unstaged: 2 patients (1.9%).

Tumor characteristics in younger women also were significantly different from tumor characteristics in older women. Younger women had tumors that were more likely to have higher stage, larger size, and progesterone receptor positive ($P < 0.05$). Tumor characteristics of the two age groups are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Tumor characteristics of the study population

Characteristic	Young women (n = 18) No. of patients (%)	Older women (n = 87) No. of patients (%)	Chi-square P-value
Tumor characteristics			
Stage			
I	1 (5.5)	12 (13.7)	<0.05
II	5 (27.7)	35 (40.2)	
III	11 (61.1)	36 (41.3)	
IV	1 (5.5)	2 (2.3)	
Unstaged	0 (0.0)	2 (2.3)	
Size			
T1	1 (5.5)	24 (27.5)	<0.05
T2	7 (38.8)	41 (47.1)	
T3	5 (27.7)	17 (19.5)	
T4	5 (27.7)	5 (5.7)	
Estrogen receptor status			
Positive	9 (50.0)	48 (55.1)	0.68
Negative	9 (50.0)	39 (44.8)	
Progesterone receptor status			

Positive	14 (77.7)	49 (56.3)	<0.05
Negative	4 (22.2)	38 (43.6)	
Nodes involved			0.11
N0	4 (22.2)	36 (41.3)	
N1	6 (33.3)	15 (17.2)	
N2	5 (27.7)	20 (22.9)	
N3	3 (16.6)	14 (16.0)	
Unknown N	0 (0.0)	2 (2.3)	
HER-2 status			0.30
Positive	13 (72.2)	72 (82.7)	
Negative	5 (27.7)	15 (17.2)	
P53 status			0.42
Positive	5 (27.7)	25 (28.7)	
Negative	13 (72.2)	62 (71.2)	

77.7% of the younger women had positive lymph nodes, as compared to 56.3% of the older women. Although this difference was not significant ($P = 0.111$), it shows an increasing trend in younger patients. 14 (77.7%) of 18 patients younger than 40 years old had positive progesterone receptor compared with 49 (56.3%) of 87 patients 40 years and older. The differences were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

The most common histologic finding was invasive ductal carcinoma, involving 92 patients (87.6%). 55 patients (59.7%) with this histology had lymph node metastasis compared to 8 out of 13 patients (61.5%) with mixed cell and other carcinomas. The

differences were not significant ($P = 0.90$). 34 out of 57 estrogen receptor positive patients (59.6%) had lymph node involvement; 29 out of 48 estrogen receptor negative patients (60.4%) had involved nodes, and the difference was not statistically significant ($P = 0.88$).

36 out of 63 progesterone receptor positive patients (57.1%) had lymph node involvement compared with 27 out of 42 progesterone receptor negative patients (64.2%). The relation between lymph node involvement and progesterone receptor status were not statistically significant ($P = 0.42$). Table 2 shows the relation between these pathologic characteristics and lymph node status.

Table 2: Statistical associations between lymph node status with size, histology, and hormone receptor status

Pathologic parameters	No. of patients with positive lymph nodes (%)	Chi-square P-value
Tumor size		<0.05
T1	11 (44.0)	
T2	28 (58.3)	
T3	15 (68.1)	
T4	9 (90.0)	
Histology		0.90
Invasive ductal carcinoma	55 (59.7)	
Invasive mixed cell + others	8 (61.5)	
Estrogen receptor status		0.88
Positive	34 (59.6)	
Negative	29 (60.4)	
Progesterone receptor status		0.42
Positive	36 (57.1)	
Negative	27 (64.2)	

We investigated the relation between progesterone receptor status and positive HER-2/neu. 38 out of 42 patients (90.4%) with negative progesterone receptor status had positive HER-2/neu, while progesterone receptor positive patients that had positive HER-2/neu were 47 out of 63 patients (74.6%). Negative progesterone receptor status was associated with HER-2 overexpression and this relation was statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

Comparing estrogen receptor status with HER-2/neu expression, just 38 out of 48 patients with negative estrogen receptor (79.1%) had positive HER-2/neu while 47 out of 57 patients with positive estrogen receptor (82.4%) had positive HER-2/neu. No statistically significant difference was found in the frequency of positive HER-2/neu tumors between the negative and positive estrogen receptor tumors (Table 3).

Table 3: Relation of HER-2/neu expression with hormone receptor status

Hormone receptor	No. of patients with negative HER-2/neu (%)	No. of patients with positive HER-2/neu (%)	Chi-square P-value
Estrogen receptor status			0.14
Positive	10 (17.5)	47 (82.4)	
Negative	10 (20.8)	38 (79.1)	
Progesterone receptor status			<0.05
Positive	16 (25.4)	47 (74.6)	
Negative	4 (9.5)	38 (90.4)	

A significant correlation was not found between the positive lymph nodes, size, or stage with estrogen receptor, progesterone receptor status, P53, or HER-2/neu expression.

Discussion

Clinically, the relation between tumor size and lymph node involvement is well known and it is the only most powerful indicator of poor prognosis in breast cancer. [9] Pathologic data consisting of patients with breast cancer shows that, at diagnosis, presence of tumor-infiltrated lymph nodes is common, with estimates ranging from 30% to 50% of cases, depending on tumor size. [10,11]

The younger women had tumors that were clearly different from tumors in older women and were characterized by unfavorable biologic parameters. The result of our research accounts for the significant within-stage disparity between the younger and older women. The majority of tumors in younger women had positive progesterone receptor and higher stage. There is a relation between all of these features and more aggressive tumors and poorer prognosis. Another analysis also found that tumors in young women have lower ER positivity, higher HER-2/epidermal growth factor receptor expression, and a trend toward inferior disease-free survival. [5] All of these studies support the concept that tumors developing in younger women are biologically different from tumors in older women and tend to be more aggressive with unfavorable biologic markers. Many studies from Europe and America have been reported showing that young age at diagnosis is as an independent predictor of poor survival.

The risk factor profile in young women is worse than older women. Young women had a tendency to have larger tumor sizes, more positive lymph nodes, more negative hormone receptors, higher tumor grades than older women. [12,13,14,15,16] This issue remains controversial, as in a retrospective study of breast cancer patients from Singapore Chia et al suggested that young women with breast cancer had a better survival than older females. [17] It is also in contrast to our study's finding that younger women were more likely to have progesterone receptor positive tumors. Moreover according to our results negative progesterone receptor tumors had a tendency to

have HER-2 over expression. As in our study, Winstanley et al [18] have not found a significant association between estrogen or progesterone receptor and lymph node status.

Conclusion

Breast cancer in younger age groups is more aggressive than in older age groups. Although negative progesterone receptor tumors were more likely to have HER-2 overexpression, different biologic behaviour of breast cancer in younger age groups may be due to progesterone receptor positive status. Additional studies should focus on association between hormone receptor status, HER-2 expression, and lymph nodes metastasis.

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